

TEST BEAM FACILITIES WEBSITE AND DATABASE USER MANUAL v.2.0

Pierre Pelissou, Blerina Gkotse, Federico Ravotti (CERN EP-DT)

Version 2.0, 10/04/2024

CERN [EDMS 3083338](#) Zenodo: [10.5281/zenodo.11058252](#)

This data management tool, created during the AIDA-2020 project (2015-2020) is intended to provide information of test beam facilities at CERN and worldwide and it is now maintained by the developers' team within the follow-up project AIDAInnova (2021-2025). In 2024 the website has been upgraded to improve computing security feature to up-to-date standards. This document is the updated version of the original User Manual proving a quick guide about how to navigate and use this website.

- 1. Homepage
 - a. Browse CERN Facilities

b. Test beam Facilities Map View

c. Test beam Facilities Database

TEST BEAM FACILITIES DATABASE

Welcome to the Test Beam Facilities Database.
This website hosts information about facilities for beam testing at CERN, in EU, and worldwide.

[CERN FACILITIES](#) [DATABASE](#) [FACILITIES MAP](#)

Click here to go to the worldwide Irradiation Facilities Database

This website is under construction and its content has been compiled from a variety of sources. Data accuracy and completeness relies on the information submitted by the facility coordinators.

2. Test beam Facilities Database

Test Beamlines Database

This database contains a list of several different Test-Beam Facilities available at CERN, in Europe and Worldwide.

Search by Country: All | Search by Particle Type: All

Click here to view all the facilities in the database.

Use filters by:

- 1) Country
- 2) Particle Type

CERN Accelerating science AIDA 2020

SUBSCRIBE IN THE DATABASE HOME CERN DIRECTORY EURO-LABS TA DATABASE USER GUIDE TERMS OF USE CONTACT

Test Beamlines Database

This database contains a list of several different Test-Beam Facilities available at CERN, in Europe and Worldwide.

Search by Country: All Search by Particle Type: All

Show All

Log In to Edit Data

Facility Name	Institute Name	Beamline Name	Country	Particle Type	Particle Energy	Coordinator
CERN PS	CERN	T9	Switzerland	electrons, hadrons, muons	0.5 - 10 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch
CERN PS	CERN	T10	Switzerland	hadrons, muons	up to 10 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch
CERN SPS	CERN	H2	Switzerland	electrons, protons,	10-400 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch

Click to one of these to display all details for the chosen facility.

CERN Test-Beam Facilities Database - Google Chrome

test-beam-facilities.web.cern.ch/facilityDetailsOut.php?f=0&ID=2&Facility=CERN%20PS

Convert to PDF

Facility coordinator contact information

Name: H.Wilens

E-mail*: sps.coordinator@cern.ch

Alternative e-mail:

Phone:

Institute/Organization Details

Institute Name: CERN

Facility Name: CERN PS

Address: route de Meyrin

City: Geneva

Country: Switzerland

Website: ps-schedule.cern.ch

Source Data

Name: PS East Area

Number of beamlines: 3

User community (HEP R&D, experiments, photon science, ..): HEP CR, R&D

Safety

FORM FIELD	YES	NO	N/A	See Comments
Is a Medical Certificate required?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="button" value="See Comments"/>
Mandatory CERN RP Training certificate?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="button" value="See Comments"/>
Should you bring your own CERN Dosimeter?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="button" value="See Comments"/>

Comments:

Accessibility

Status: Active

Booking slots: Typically Wednesday to Wednesday

Access selection & procedure (Committee, ...): SPSC or LHCC if more than 2 weeks

Availability: Up-time & shutdowns: No beam in 2019 and 2020

Special Agreements:

Agreement Details:

Funding programs:

Comments:

Additional Comments

Comments: 2

a. Create and edit facility information

Step 1: register in the facility coordinators e-group

Click here to send a pre-filled email to be part of the facility coordinator e-group.

TEST BEAM FACILITIES DATABASE

Welcome to the Test Beam Facilities Database.
This website hosts information about facilities for beam testing at CERN, in EU, and worldwide.

CERN FACILITIES DATABASE FACILITIES MAP

This website is under construction and its content has been compiled from a variety of sources. Data accuracy and completeness relies on the information submitted by the facility coordinators.

The test beam facilities database's team will review your request and include your email address in this e-group. Due to some synchronization time, this step can take around an hour after your message will be treated.

Step 2: log in

Test Beamlines Database

This database contains a list of several different Test-Beam Facilities available at CERN, in Europe and Worldwide.

Search by Country: All Search by Particle Type: All

Show All

Click here to log in.

Log In to Edit Data

Facility Name	Institute Name	Beamline Name	Country	Particle Type	Particle Energy	Coordinator
CERN PS	CERN	T9	Switzerland	electrons, hadrons, muons	0.5 - 10 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch
CERN PS	CERN	T10	Switzerland	hadrons, muons	up to 10 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch
CERN SPS	CERN	H2	Switzerland	electrons, protons,	10-400GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch

Make sure to use the same email address included in the e-group (step 1).

Facility coordinators need to log in through the CERN authentication system (CERN Single Sign-On) to update or insert the data of a test beam facility. After clicking on the button, you will be redirected to this page where there are various possibilities to log in described in the picture below:

The image shows the CERN Single Sign-On login page. The page header includes 'CERN Accelerating science' on the left and 'Directory' on the right. The main title is 'CERN Single Sign-On'. The page is divided into three main sections for login:

- Sign in with a CERN account:** Includes fields for 'Username' and 'Password', a 'Sign In' button, and a 'Forgot Password?' link. A red box highlights this section with the annotation 'Through a CERN account (if you have one)'.
- Sign in with your email or organisation:** Includes buttons for 'Home organisation - eduGAIN' and 'External email - Guest access'. A red box highlights this section with the annotation 'Through an organization / institution account'.
- Sign in with a social account:** Includes buttons for 'Google', 'LinkedIn', 'GitHub', and 'Facebook'. A red box highlights this section with the annotation 'Through a public service account'.

Below these sections, there is a link for 'Or use another login method' with options for 'Two-factor authentication' and 'Kerberos'. At the bottom, there is a disclaimer: 'By logging in, you agree to comply with the CERN Computing Rules, in particular OCS. CERN implements the measures necessary to ensure compliance.'

The footer contains links for 'Account (Manage your account)', 'Privacy (Privacy Notice)', and 'Support (Service Desk - +41 22 76 77777, Service Status)'. The CERN logo is in the bottom right corner.

NB: In case none of the three mentioned solutions works, please create a CERN Lightweight account following this procedure using with your personal e-mail: <https://account.cern.ch/account/Externals/>.

Step 3: INSERT a new Irradiation Facility entry

After logging in with the same email address as in step 1, use the button “New Test Beam Facility” on the right-hand side of the screen.

A new window opens where you can fill all the requested information.

Please note that the e-mail field must not be empty. It must only be filled in with the same e-mail address of the person (facility coordinator) registered in the e-group that will have the right to log in and modify the data. Also, note that if you select an e-mail address different from the one used for the current login (e.g. to transfer the rights to handle the data to another colleague), from this point on, you will need to come back to step 1 and request the newly selected e-mail to be added in the e-group.

By pressing the “Confirm” button, an automatic e-mail summarizing the entry will be sent to you and the database administrator. The data will be saved in the database but not made public yet.

Once the data are approved, the (assigned) facility coordinator will receive a confirmation e-mail and the Test Beam Facility information will be publicly available. After the confirmation, the facility coordinator can log in and modify the data.

Step 3.1: Insert a Beamline entry

Once the test beam entry is saved and approved, you can add the beamline details:

The screenshot shows the 'Facilities Database' page. At the top, there are navigation links: SUBSCRIBE IN THE DATABASE, HOME, CERN DIRECTORY, EURO-LABS TA, DATABASE, USER GUIDE, TERMS OF USE, CONTACT. Below the navigation is a search area with 'Search by Country' and 'Search by Particle Type' dropdown menus, both set to 'All', and a 'Show All' button. A table lists existing beamlines. A red box highlights the 'New Beamline' button with the text 'Click here to add a new beamline entry.'

Facility Name	Institute Name	Beamline Name	Country	Particle Type	Particle Energy	Coordinator Email
CERN PS	CERN	T9	Switzerland	electrons, hadrons, muons	0.5 - 10 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch
CERN PS	CERN	T10	Switzerland	hadrons, muons	up to 10 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch
CERN SPS	CERN	H2	Switzerland	electrons, protons	10-400 GeV/c	sps.coordinator@cern.ch

The screenshot shows the 'Edit beamline' form. The 'Beamline:' section is highlighted in orange. The form contains several input fields:

- Testbeam: CERN PS (dropdown)
- Beamline name: Beamline name...
- Particle type: Electrons, hadrons, muons...
- Particle polarity: positive, negative...
- Particle type details: Details...
- Particle intensity: Intensity...
- Particle Momentum/Energy: Particle Momentum/Energy of the beam
- Particle Momentum/Energy Resolution: Momentum/Energy/Energy resolution of the beam ...
- Experiments per beamline: 1,2,3,...
- Experiments per beamline details: Details...

The screenshot shows the 'Edit beamline' form, specifically the 'Infrastructure:' section. It features a table with columns for 'FORM FIELD', 'YES', 'NO', 'N/A', and 'See Comments'. Below the table is a 'Comments:' field and a 'Confirm' button highlighted with a red box and the text 'Click here to confirm.'

FORM FIELD	YES	NO	N/A	See Comments
Trigger signal & system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tracker & Telescopes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Geometser service	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Magnets	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Slow Control	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Vacuum pipe	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Handling service(cranes,...)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Movable stages	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Electricity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cabling infrastructure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Particle ID instrumentations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IT services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Step 4: UPDATE a Test Beam Facility entry

To edit your facility information, you must log in first (see Step 1). An additional icon will appear next to the test beam and beamline entries that you can edit.

The screenshot shows the 'Facilities Database' interface. At the top, there are navigation links: SUBSCRIBE IN THE DATABASE, HOME, CERN DIRECTORY, EURO-LABS TA, DATABASE, USER GUIDE, TERMS OF USE, CONTACT. Below the navigation is a search area with 'Search by Country' (set to Germany) and 'Search by Particle Type' (set to All), with a 'Show All' button.

The main table lists facilities with columns: Facility Name, Institute Name, Beamline Name, Country, Particle Type, Particle Energy, Coordinator Email, and Show entry. The first row is 'DESY Test Beam Facility' with a pencil icon in the 'Beamline Name' column. A red box with the text 'Click here to edit' points to this icon.

Below the table are two detail pages. The left page is 'Add Facility' with a 'Contact Information' section containing fields for Name, Email, Alternative email, Phone, and Coordinator phone number, with a 'Next' button. The right page is 'Add Facility' with an 'Additional comments' section and two buttons: 'Delete request' and 'Confirm'. A red box with the text 'Click here to confirm the updates.' points to the 'Confirm' button. Another red box with the text 'Click here to request to delete the data and an e-mail message will be automatically generated.' points to the 'Delete request' button.

Facility Name	Institute Name	Beamline Name	Country	Particle Type	Particle Energy	Coordinator Email	Show entry
DESY Test Beam Facility	DESY	Beamline	Germany	electrons (prm.)	6.3 GeV/c	testbeam-coor@desy.de	
ELSA	University of Bonn	Beamline	Germany	electrons	1.2 - 3.2 GeV/c	elsner@physik.uni-bonn.de	

After pressing on the "Confirm" button, the data will not be visible until the database administrator approves them.

The screenshot shows the 'Facilities Database' interface. At the top, there are navigation links: 'SUBSCRIBE IN THE DATABASE', 'HOME', 'CERN DIRECTORY', 'EURO-LABS TA', 'DATABASE', 'USER GUIDE', 'TERMS OF USE', and 'CONTACT'. The main content area features a search section with 'Search by Country' (set to 'Germany') and 'Search by Particle Type' (set to 'All'), followed by a 'Show All' button. Below this is a table of facilities. A red box highlights the 'Beamline' column header, with an arrow pointing to a pencil icon in the 'Beamline' column of the first row. A callout box says 'Click here to edit.' Below the table is an 'Edit beamline' form with various input fields.

Facility Name	Institute Name	Beamline Name	Country	Particle Type	Particle Energy	Coordinator Email	Show entry
DESYII Test Beam Facility	DESY	Beamline	Germany	electrons (prim.)	6.3 GeV/c	testbeam-coor@desy.de	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ELSA	University of Bonn	Beamline	Germany	electrons	1.2 - 3.2 GeV/c	etsner@physik.uni-bonn.de	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
MAMI	University of Mainz	Beamline	Germany	electrons	< 1.6 GeV/c	fischer@kph.uni-mainz.de	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Edit beamline

Beamline:

Testbeam:
Test Beam Facility: [dropdown]

Beamline name:
Test Beamline: [input]

Particle type:
Protons: [input]

Particle polarity:
positive, negative...: [input]

Particle type details:
Details...: [input]

Particle intensity:
Intensity...: [input]

Particle Momentum Energy:
Particle Momentum Energy of the beam: [input]

Particle Momentum Energy Resolution:
Momentum Energy Resolution of the beam...: [input]

Experiments per beamline:
0: [input]

2. Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under GA no 101004761.